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Executive Summary

Box 1: Report Highlights

- Proto type light-emitting devices for use on trawl fishing gears have been developed and tested
- Laboratory experiments investigating the behavioural response of haddock and cod to light of different wavelengths, intensity and strobing rates.
- Continuous lines of light have been shown to influence the height at which some species enter a trawl gear
- Illuminated grids in the extension section can be used to direct fish out of the trawl gear or to different codends where further selection can take place.
- Adding white and purple LED lights into baited traps significantly improved the catch per unit effort of snow crab

Box 2: The methods/approaches followed

- Design and development of physical hardware, software and user interfaces.
- Laboratory experiments with captive fish.
- Catch comparison fishing trials.

Box 3: How these results can be used and by who?

- Fishers and net makers – to develop gears that utilise light to select for fish that best match their quota allocation.
- Fishing gear scientists – to better understand how light can be harnessed to improve trawl gear selectivity and the fishing efficiency of traps.

Box 4: Policy recommendations

- This report demonstrates the potential of using light to improve the selective performance of gears, which if to be fully exploited requires (i) committed research support and (ii) a regulatory framework that is sufficiently flexible to accept readily new technologies and novel gears.

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In this deliverable we report on the potential use of underwater light to modify the behavioural reaction of fish to trawl gears. We focus on (i) technological developments, (ii) laboratory experiments on fish behaviour and (iii) experimental trials at sea.

1 Technological developments

SafetyNet Technologies (SNTech) has spent most of its time and effort during the DiscardLess project designing and building light-emitting devices for use in scientific trials. These trials have focused on equipping fishing gears (predominantly trawls) with light of different specifications (varying wavelength, intensity and flash rate) in order to see how, if at all, it alters the behavioural response of different species of fish and other organisms in the ocean environment. During this time, SNTech have designed a range of prototypes for direct use in fishing gears, but also for use in the lab environment to facilitate these behavioural experiments. They have been designed to be easy to use and to have minimal impact on usual fishing practices. This development process has led to us designing physical hardware, software and user interfaces.

While lights have previously been tested in the context of commercial fishing gears, the light-emitting devices have usually been sourced from existing products that have often not been designed specifically for commercial fishing practices. Such devices are also limited in their ability to produce a range of specific light emissions, with little or no control over the light characteristics (eg. Wavelength, intensity, flash rate). The experiments being conducted during the DiscardLess project required a higher degree of control over exactly how the light was emitted, in which geometries it could be deployed on the fishing gear, and how robust it was in the marine (and specifically fishing) environment.

SNTech worked with Marine Scotland Science to understand the types of devices they wanted, the application of those devices, and how the light could be controlled within the bounds of their experimental requirements. These end-user requirements informed a design and prototyping process that has now led to outcomes that enable a range of experiments that would previously not have been possible.

1.1 Matrix

The Matrix device was designed to be used for laboratory behavioural experiments. It comprises 10 waterproof LED ribbons that can be programmed to emit different colours of lights at different intensities. Each tentacle is 3m long, with RGB LEDs spaced 10cm apart along the length. This enabled tank testing to explore how different fish species might respond to light stimuli. It is controlled by a DMX light board, which uses sliders (similar to theatrical equipment) (Figure 1). However, the unit can also be controlled via a laptop to programme in temporally-defined patterns.

Figure 1. The controllable light Matrix and DMX light board system

1.2 Fibre Optic Light Lines

SNTech build a light emitting pod that can be connected to a length of fibre optic cable in order to produce an illuminated “rope” that can be attached to a trawl, trawl-gear (such as a sorting grid) or other fishing gears. A simple to use programming system was also built to enable direct control of the LED light sources by scientists deploying the device, enabling light across the visible spectrum (red-violet), intensities (1-255 brightness levels) and flash rate (Hz) to be configured and deployed through the fibre.

Figure 2. Light emitting unit to illuminate a length of side-emitting fibre optic. The unit is has 2 LEDs so the fibre can be illuminated from both ends for a more even glow.

Figure 3. Fibre optic cable illuminated by light pod.

1.3 Optical Fibre-Threaded SMP

Side-emitting optical fibres were hand-woven into a section of a square mesh panel (SMP) which was fitted to the extension section of a trawl. The fibres were 1.5mm in diameter and illuminated using a LED light pod. Some interesting points became apparent concerning the directionality of the light versus its visibility to the camera.

Figure 4. The 1.5 mm side emitting optical fibres woven into the netting twine of a SMP

1.4 LED Light Lines

Three 10m lengths of RGB LED strips were inserted into a length of transparent, reinforced plastic hosing, which was then filled with clear mineral oil and connected to a control cable to enable the LEDs to be controlled from a control-pod. The resulting “rope” looked a bit like Christmas tree lights, and each LED is individually programmable. This means it is possible, not only to specify the colour, intensity and flash rate, but also patterns along the length of “rope” enabling animated sequences to be programmed. Furthermore, each LED can be programmed to broadcast light at a uniform brightness, meaning more control over experimental variables.

Figure 5. The LED light lines where each of the LEDs are individually programmable.

2 Laboratory experiments

The wavelength, intensity, polarisation and strobing of light are all known to influence the behaviour of fish (Ben-Yami, 1976; Marchesan et al., 2005; Arimoto et al., 2010; Königson, 2002; Patrick et al., 1985). And in order to have a systematic approach for using light technologies to improve fishing gear selectivity and to reduce the by-catch of unwanted species we need a better understanding of how these light parameter settings may affect fish escape behaviour. To help achieve this the following laboratory based experiments were carried out.

2.1 Investigating the use of coloured LED lights to stimulate an escape response in haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*)

This experiment was used to determine whether the presence of coloured LED lights on a large mesh panel would affect the rate at which haddock pass through the panel compared to a panel that was not illuminated by lights. Fish were conditioned to swim between two feeding stations

positioned at opposite ends of the tank using a food reward and white spot lights as an indicator the food was about to be presented similar to the method used in Glass et al. (1993). Conditioning allowed the directed movement of the fish to encounter the mesh panel and reactions of the fish were recorded. The large mesh panel only covered half the width of the tank and enabled 3 behaviours to be observed throughout the experiment; pass through the panel, refuse to pass through the panel or actively avoid the panel (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Experimental tank set-up showing the 3 behaviours observed throughout the trials; 1) actively avoid the panel, 2) refuse to pass through the panel or 3) pass through the panel. Station 1 and 2 show the position of the white spot lights used to signal to the fish food was present and initiate controlled movement of the fish during trials.

18 fully grown haddock (length range 30-50cm) were used. Video analysis allowed the 3 behaviours to be counted under each lighting configuration. Three colours of light were tested; green, blue and red, either flashing or constant and a control with no lights (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The LED light panel tested when illuminated in green, red and blue.

A generalized linear model (GLM) with Poisson distribution was used to analyse the data and no significant effect was detected between the different coloured lights and the number of passes through the panel. All fish on early exposure were unwilling to pass through the panel. However visual observations showed a clear behavioural difference of naïve fish when exposed to the blue light as a very strong aversive response. Habituation to all colours of lights whether flashing or constant and the panel itself was established throughout the trials as the number of passes through the panel increased with the number of exposures to the panel whether illuminated or not (Figure 8). The total number of passes through the panel over the course of the trials was low therefore reducing the power of the statistical analysis to draw any solid conclusions but provided a useful insight into how to proceed with future experiments.

Figure 8. Number of passes through the panel observed at each trial in order of sequence the trials were carried out, where (i) the panel was not illuminated (control) and (ii) the panel was illuminated by the coloured lights (treatment). The figures show a strong habituation effect as more passes are observed the more times the fish are exposed to the panel.

2.2 Investigating the reaction distance of haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) to coloured LED lights

Due to the lack of passes through the large mesh panel in the previous trials, this experiment was designed to focus solely on the behaviour of the fish in relation to the lights. This was done by removing the large mesh panel and simply having a string of LED lights hanging at one end of the tank and measuring the mean distance of all the fish in the tank from the light at set intervals throughout the trials (Figure 9). Three groups of 8 haddock were used, with 3 different coloured LED lights; green, blue and red. Each group of fish was presented with a random order of light configurations 3 times a day for 3 days. 3 control measurements of mean distance were taken while the light was off and then 9 treatment observations were made at set intervals while the light was on. The video recordings of these trials have been processed and these data will be analysed determine any changes in distribution throughout a trial with and without the light on. The mean distance of fish at each interval per colour will be compared within batch and between batches of fish.

Figure 9. Image showing the string of LED lights hanging at one end of the tank and haddock swimming nearby.

2.3 Investigating the reaction distances of cod (*Gadus morhua*) to coloured LED lights

The above trials were replicated with 3 groups of 8 cod but these data are yet to be analysed. These individual trials however lasted significantly longer than the haddock trials as the cod showed a much stronger aversive response to the lights with each trial lasting 30 minutes compared to 10 minutes as observed with the haddock.

The same fish used for these trials are currently being re-used for light intensity trials with the same set-up as the coloured light trials except 3 intensities of blue light are being tested instead of 3 colours of light.

We also plan to investigate the effect of strobe lighting at a future date as this has currently only been tested in the haddock mesh panel work. It would be interesting to see if there is a difference in habituation to the lights between a strobed light and a light that is on constantly. It is clear from the trials currently completed the fish are quick to become habituated to the light of all colours and intensities.

3 Experimental trials at sea

A number of experimental trials were held to investigate how light may influence how fish will react in trawl gears. These trials used fibre optic cables that were illuminated by an LED pod and which supplied a continuous line of light. The cables were attached to the footrope, the leading edge of a separator panel or to a rigid grid fitted to the extension section of the trawl.

3.1 Fibre optic cables illuminating the footrope and a horizontal separator panel

Material and Methods

Two sets of experimental trials to investigate the effect that a continuous line of light may have on the behavioural reaction of fish in the mouth of a trawl were carried out on the MRV Alba na Mara during September 2014 and during March 2015 (coinciding with the autumnal and spring equinoxes). The trials were carried out on the same fishing grounds approximately 10 nautical miles east of the Orkney Islands, Scotland at depths of between 75 -85m. A Marine Scotland BT201 demersal prawn trawl fitted with a horizontal separator panel in the mouth of the trawl and leading to two separate codends (Figure 10) was fished and all tows were between 45 – 75 minutes long. The line of light was supplied by a 5mm diameter multi-strand side emitting fibre optic cable that was illuminated by a unit which houses a single green (530nm wavelength) LED and was powered by a 12V DC supply. The cable was 30m long and protected by 12mm diameter clear PVC hose tubing (Figure 11).

Figure 10. A demersal trawl fitted with a horizontal separator panel leading to two separate codends. The second two images portray the illuminated side emitting fibre optic cable attached to the fishing line and the leading edge of the separator panel respectively.

Figure 11. The LED unit and the illuminated fibre optic cable. And a still frame from video footage identifying the illuminated fibre optic cable on the leading edge of the separator panel and the groundgear attached to the fishing line.

The first set of trials took place during daylight hours. The separator panel was laced in along the selvedge, the leading edge of which sat naturally at 80cm above the fishing line. The panel was fished (i) in its natural configuration of 80cm and (ii) with a restrictor rope between the fishing line and the centre of the leading edge of the panel. When the restrictor rope was used, the leading edge of the panel had a height of 20cm in the centre section rising to 80cm at the selvedges. The fibre optic cable was permanently attached to the leading edge of the separator panel and the two gear configurations were tested both with and without the cable illuminated.

For the second set of trials the height of the separator panel was reduced by lacing it into the netting panels below the selvedges, so that its leading edge sat at 40cm above the fishing line. It

was expected that appreciable proportions of cod and flat fish species would swim both above and below the panel at this height. In addition, the trials were carried during night time hours to maximise the contrast between the unlit ambient case and the case when the lines were illuminated. To test the effect of the position of the line of light, the fibre optic cable was fitted to the leading edge of the separator panel and to the centre section of the fishing line.

Results

In the first set of trials the illuminated cable had little effect. It was attached to the leading edge of a separator panel that was fished at its natural height of 80 cm or with its centre section restricted to 20cm above the fishing line and only influenced common dab (Figure 12).

Figure 12. The proportion of fish entering above the panel for the four gear configuration of the September 2014 trials.

During the second set of trials the fibre optic cable had a significant effect on how haddock, whiting, plaice, common dab and gurnards entered the trawl. Here the cable was attached either to the fishing line or to the leading edge of a separator panel set at a height of 40 cm and more of these species swam below the panel when the cables were illuminated (Figure 13).

Figure 13. The proportion of fish entering above the panel for the three gear configuration of the March 2015 trials.

3.2 Fibre optic cables illuminating rigid grids in the extension section

Material and Methods

Two further sets of experimental trials were carried out on the MRV Alba na Mara during March 2016 and March 2017 to investigate the effect that an illuminated grid may have on the behavioural reaction of fish in the extension section of a demersal trawl. The trials took place on fishing grounds approximately 10 nautical miles east of Aberdeen, Scotland using a Marine Scotland BT201 demersal trawl, at depths ranging from 79 to 104 meters.

The grid was made from 25mm thick HDPE and measured 1.2 x 0.75 m, it had a horizontal bar that divided the grid in half and vertical bars set 0.145 m apart. Two 5mm multi-strand side emitting fibre optic cables housed in 12mm clear PVC tubing were cable tied to the grid, one illuminating the upper half and the other illuminating the lower half. The cables could be illuminated by a light pod unit which houses a single green (530nm wavelength) LED and is powered by a 12V DC supply.

During the 2016 trials the grid was mounted at a 60 degree angle near the start of the extension. A panel of 80mm diamond mesh netting was attached behind the central bar of the grid and fitted along the selvages of the extension leading to two separate 80mm codends. Fish that went through the top half of the grid were retained in the upper codend and those that went through the bottom half were retained in the lower one (Figure 14). Four different lighting configurations were investigated: (i) all of the grid illuminated; (ii) top-half of grid illuminated; (iii) bottom-half of grid illuminated; and (iv) no illumination (Figure 15). Furthermore, the tows took place between midday and midnight ensuring that half of each days tows took place during daylight hours and half during the night.

Figure 14. The gear configuration during the 2016 trials where fish that went through the top half of the grid were retained in the upper codend and those that went through the bottom half were retained in the lower one.

Figure 15. The ways the grid was illuminated during the 2016 trials.

During the 2017 trials the grid was mounted horizontally in the panel that vertically separated the extension section. A circular metal ring was fitted at the beginning of the extension section to hold the netting open. The front end of the separator panel was fitted to a horizontal cross bar on the ring and the grid was installed into the panel, 12 meshes aft of the ring. In addition an 80mm diamond mesh guiding panel was fitted from the cross bar to either the top or bottom netting sheets a position 1.85 m ahead of the ring. When the guiding panel was attached to the top sheet, fish were directed into the lower half of the extension from where they could either swim up through the grid and to the upper codend or swim past the grid to the lower codend. Similarly, when the guiding panel was attached to the bottom sheet, fish were directed to the upper half of the extension from where they could swim down through the grid and onto the lower codend or

past the grid to the upper codend (Figure 16). Four different configurations were tested during these trials: (i) illuminated grid in top sheet (Figure 17); (ii) non-illuminated grid in top sheet; (iii) illuminated grid in bottom sheet; and (iv) non-illuminated grid in bottom sheet. These tows all took place between the hours of 8:00 and 17:15.

Figure 16. The gear configuration during the 2017 trials where the guiding panel was attached to (i) the top sheet or (ii) to the bottom sheet.

Figure 17. Image of the illuminated grid in top sheet.

Results

The results of the 2016 inclined grid trials are summarised very well by the bulk data and demonstrate that, in general, as illumination increases, more fish pass through the lower half of the grid. This is particularly the case for the flatfish where the proportion of fish going into the lower codend increases (i) when the grids are illuminated and (ii) during the daytime. For haddock and whiting this is only evident when the grids are lit and there does not appear to be much of a day-night effect. For cod the illuminated grids appear to have some effect at night but not during the day (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Some pairwise comparisons of the proportion of fish entering above the panel for the four gear configuration of the 2016 trials.

The results of the 2017 trials where the grid was mounted horizontally in the panel that vertically separated the extension section, illuminating the grid in the lower sheet led to significantly more fish of all species (except cod) passing through it than when it was unlit. When the grid was in the top sheet only whiting and common dab were affected and illuminating the grid reduced the number of whiting but increased the number of common dab which passed through.

Figure 19. Some pairwise comparisons of the proportion of fish entering above the panel for the four gear configuration of the 2017 trials.

Haddock are significantly more likely to pass through a grid that is in the top sheet rather than in the bottom sheet, whereas lemon sole, plaice and long rough dab are more likely to pass through a grid in the bottom sheet. There is no significant difference in the proportion of cod or common dab that pass through the grids in either top or bottom positions. For whiting the situation is more complex. When the grids are illuminated more of them will go through a grid in the lower sheet but when the grids are unlit more will go through a grid in the upper sheet.

3.3 LED Lights on Shrimp Trawls

Technological innovation has reduced bycatch rates in bottom trawl fisheries, but problems still exist in the area of bycatch of small-bodied fishes. In this study, we propose to test the effectiveness of artificial lighting at reducing capture rates of small-bodied fish in shrimp trawls. We will conduct a field experiment, comparing the effectiveness of five commercially-available light colors at improving selectivity of shrimp trawls in Atlantic waters. We will examine whether species-specific responses are observed across colors, and use underwater cameras to directly observe fish response in situ to each configuration. Our goal is to determine whether lighting can serve as a conservation tool in Atlantic fisheries, and how best to use lights to minimize bycatch.

Material and Methods

The commercial twin-trawler F/V Atlantic Charger (69' LOA) was chartered in late summer to assist with the comparative fishing experiment. The research team joined the vessel in late July at the port of Cottesville, located on the northeast coast of Newfoundland. Two identical inshore shrimp trawls were measured on the wharf to document quality control and ensure the trawls were identical in all regards. Low-powered LED's were installed on the fishing line of one of the trawls at intervals of 1.2m in the manner identical to Hannah et al. (2015) (Figure 20).

Trip One (August 1-2, 2015): A total of 3 paired tows were conducted at a depth of 250-276 fathoms. The experimental trawl was lit with green LED lights on the fishing line while the control was unlit (i.e., no lights).

Trip Two (August 5-6, 2015): A total of 6 paired tows were conducted at a depth of 258-273 fathoms. The experimental trawl was lit with red LED lights on the fishing line while the control was unlit (i.e., no lights).

Figure 20. LED attachment and a night time photograph of the LED lights installed on the experimental trawl.

Results

Side by side tows of the experimental and control trawls produced expected trawl geometry and excellent catches of the target species – Northern shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*).

Figure 21 illustrates the Catch per Unit Effort (CPUE) of shrimp caught for each of the three treatments: unlit, green lights, and red lights. The data here represents 9 paired tows (3 in first trip with green lights, 6 in second trip with red lights). Tow lengths ranged from 147 to 325 min. (mean +/- 1 S.E. = 207 +/- 17). We express CPUE in bags/min. This represents a total of ~62 hrs of fishing.

Figure 21. Catch Per Unit Effort (bags/min) of the target species Northern shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*) for the three experimental treatments (unlit, green lights, and red lights).

For both experimental treatments (green and red lights), the CPUE for the target species was less than the control treatment (no lights). This was an unexpected finding. A functional explanation is still lacking, however we hypothesize that this species of shrimp, which is typically regarded as a poor swimmer, may have exhibited avoidance behaviour to the approaching experimental trawls. In the event the species dives in response to approaching threats, they may have escaped under the fishing line, which is elevated due to 28" mandatory toggle chains.

Based on the unexpected reduction in CPUE of the target species, the research team suspended further sea trials to determine how best to proceed. Unfortunately, during the intervening weeks, tragedy struck the industry partner, with the unexpected sinking of their vessel. No one was harmed in the sinking of the vessel, however it has produced an additional obstacle for the research team, as our preferred methodological approach requires a twin trawler, of which there are very few in the region.

Given the reduced catch rates of the target species and sinking of the vessel, the research team is currently assessing the research objectives and experimental design. We are eager to continue our field experiments this summer, but realize there is more to this shrimp species than previously thought. We are dialoguing with shrimp capture experts within DFO, NOAA, and the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife. We anticipate having a revised experimental design and budget within the very near future. Additional funding or revised research objectives may be required, but are not yet known.

3.4 Artificial lights improve the catchability of snow crab (*Chionoecetes opilio*) traps

This study investigated the behaviour and commercial catchability of snow crab (*Chionoecetes opilio*) in response to different low-powered LED lights under laboratory and field conditions.

Materials and Methods

We created a novel choice-experiment in a laboratory setting in which we investigated the behaviour of snow crab in response to coloured LED lights. The results showed that snow crab movement was dependent on light colour, with animals choosing to move toward blue and white lights, away from purple lights, and no detectable effect for green and red lights. We then conducted two field experiments to investigate the effect of the same LED lights on the catch rates of commercial traps during the 2016 snow crab fishery on the east coast of Newfoundland and Labrador. This experiment was conducted aboard an inshore fishing vessel (*F/V The Phoenix*, 10.7 m LOA) targeting snow crab, approximately 20 nautical miles southeast of Petty Harbour, Newfoundland and Labrador (Latitude between 47°14'10.56"N and 47°23'51.12"N, Longitude between 52°31'41.16"W and 52°16'50.58"W) from April 26 to May 23, 2016 (see Fig. 3). The depth at the sampling site ranged from 165 to 173 m. Small Japanese-style conical traps with a bottom diameter of 101.5 cm, top diameter of 55.5 cm, height of 44 cm, and mesh size of 135 mm were used, typical for this fishery (Figure 22). Inspection of the traps was conducted prior to sea trials to ensure the traps were identical in all aspects. Three experimental treatments were investigated: (1) Control trap – baited trap with 453 g of mixed squid and herring in a perforated plastic jar; (2) Purple Light trap – baited similar to Control trap, with the addition of a purple LED light; (3) White Light trap – baited similar to Control trap, with the addition of a white LED light.

Figure 22. Snow crab trap.

Results

Results from the first field experiment showed that adding white and purple LED lights into baited traps significantly improved Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE) by 77% and 47% respectively. Results from the second field experiment showed that unbaited traps equipped with only LED lights (no bait), could also catch snow crab in comparable amounts to traditional baited traps, with soak time and depth explaining some of the variation in CPUE. Taken together, these experiments suggest that fishing enterprises can improve their catching performance and profitability by adding LED lights to their traps, or by using LED lights as a bait replacement.

3.5 Location, orientation, and economic performance of low-powered LED lights inside snow crab traps in eastern Canada

This study investigated the effect of installing underwater Light-Emitting Diode (LED) lights in different locations and orientations inside baited traps targeting snow crab (*Chionoecetes opilio*) off the coast of Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada, as well as the economic performance associated with using lights in this fishery.

Materials and Methods

Experimental fishing was carried out utilizing the 11.89 m LOA snow crab fishing vessel, *F/V The Flat Rock Byes*, register number 154021, from May to June, 2017. The experiment was conducted in the nearshore waters of Newfoundland, directly east from the town of Pouch Cove (Latitude between 47°43'30"N and 47°47'48"N, Longitude between 52°25'15"W and 52°37'24"W). The average depth of fishing was approximately 190 to 200 m. Small Japanese-style conical traps which are typical for this fishery were used (Figure 22). All traps, including control and experimental traps, were identical in every manner. Baiting was standardized, with each trap receiving 1362 g of whole squid hung in the entrance of the trap using a snap shackle. Traps were deployed in fleets, with each fleet containing a total of 60 traps spaced at intervals of 36.6 m. The fleets were soaked for several days and haphazardly retrieved between 4-15 days, depending on the weather.

Results

Our results showed no significant differences in catch per unit effort (CPUE) for both legal and sublegal-sized crab among the different experimental treatments, however all of the experimental (illuminated) traps harvested significantly more crab than control traps (without lights). While longer soak time did not increase the CPUE for control trap, this variable significantly increased the catch rate for the illuminated trap. Proportion of legal-sized crab was 73% for both control and illuminated traps, and there were no significant differences in crab size distributions between pairwise comparisons. In terms of economic feasibility, investment of LED lights in the snow crab fishery will require additional variable costs for fishing enterprises, however our analysis suggests the financial break-even point is quickly reached. A profit of \$206,000 CDN per vessel is predicted during the life cycle of a typical light (e.g. 14 years), compared to traditional capture methods (without lights). This gain was proportional with crab prices and allocated quota level. Our results suggest that fishing enterprises could increase their profitability by using LED lights in the snow crab fishery.

4 Conclusion

These experiments demonstrate how light can be used to direct fish to different parts of a gear, to direct fish out of a gear or to attract fish towards a gear. These results are likely to be very useful, in the context of a landing obligation (or discard ban), as they demonstrate the possibility of developing gears whose selectivity can be modified easily between tows (eg by switching on a light cable or an LED, or adjusting headline height) in response to the population on the ground and a vessels individual quota allocation. However, they also demonstrate that we must not have an over-simplified view, as fish reactions will be species specific and are likely to have seasonal and environmental dependencies.

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